

genomicrelatedness

bwRSE4HPC Project Report

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Project Partners:	Gisela Kopp ² , Till Dorendorf ³
Scientific field:	Biology
Subfield:	Bioinformatics
Start:	2025-10-01
Duration:	3 months
Type of Work:	Refactoring, packaging, documentation, and workflow standardization
License:	MIT
Link:	https://github.com/nf-core/genomicrelatedness/
Programming Language:	Nextflow, Python
Technologies:	nf-core
Target Cluster:	BinAC2

1. Executive Summary

This bwRSE4HPC-project [1,2] aimed to modernize and modularize an existing Nextflow [3] pipeline that was originally developed for relatedness analysis from low-coverage whole-genome sequencing (lcWGS) data [4], specifically in wild Guinea fowl.

Problem Statement: The original [relatedness analysis workflow](#) was monolithic, based on outdated Nextflow DSL1 code, and difficult to maintain or reuse beyond the original project context. This limited reproducibility, portability, and community adoption.

Solution: We implemented a new pipeline from scratch and aligned it with nf-core [5] standards. The resulting pipeline, [nf-core/genomicrelatedness](#), modernizes the complete workflow using Nextflow DSL2, modular components, and standardized project structure. We also prepared user-facing usage instructions for BinAC2 to support practical HPC execution.

Impact: The proposal for the pipeline was accepted by nf-core and the project is now available there. At the time of writing, the pipeline is still marked as “under development”, with only a few remaining tasks before a v1.0 release. This work establishes a sustainable and community-facing basis for relatedness estimation from low-coverage sequencing data and substantially improves long-term maintainability and usability.

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Figure 1: Official logo of the `nf-core/genomicrelatedness` pipeline.

2. Description of Work

2.1. Initial Problem

The `original codebase` consisted of legacy DSL1 workflows that were tightly coupled and hard to extend. Missing modular boundaries and limited automation reduced developer productivity and made quality assurance difficult. In addition, the workflow was not integrated into nf-core, which created barriers for wider adoption and constrained reuse in standardized bioinformatics environments. The initial project work plan can be found in Ref. [6].

2.2. Solution Design

The core design decision was to reimplement the pipeline as a new DSL2-based nf-core pipeline rather than applying incremental patching to the legacy implementation. This enabled:

- Clear module boundaries and better maintainability
- Compatibility with nf-core conventions for structure, linting, and release processes
- Easier portability across local and HPC execution profiles
- Long-term sustainability through community standards

Where possible, nf-core conventions and reusable components were adopted. Custom implementation was retained where domain-specific behavior was required.

2.3. Contributions

The following contributions were provided during the project:

- Full pipeline rewrite from scratch into the new `genomicrelatedness` pipeline
- Migration to Nextflow DSL2 and modular workflow structure
- Alignment with nf-core development and contribution workflow
- Successful `proposal acceptance` in nf-core and publication as `nf-core/genomicrelatedness`
- Preparation of user instructions for running the pipeline on BinAC2 bwHPC cluster
- Project documentation improvements to support onboarding and operational use

External Constraints for Additional Relatedness Tools The original plan included integration of additional relatedness estimation software, but in several cases this was blocked by external constraints such as unclear or missing licenses, or required [7,8] file format conversion software that was either unlicensed or not properly packaged. These constraints are outside project control, but the modular pipeline design now makes future integration straightforward once those tooling and licensing issues are resolved.

2.4. Showcase

The pipeline's [nf-core website](#) presents documentation, usage examples and parameters (see Figure 2) in such a way that onboarding of new users is as easy as it gets.

(a) Workflow schematic metro map.

(b) Parameters section at [nf-core](#).

Figure 2: Pipeline documentation on its [GitHub](#) page and <https://nf-co.re/>

With Nextflow and nf-core installed (standard), the pipeline can then simply be run via

```
nf-core pipelines launch nf-core/genomicrelatedness -params-file <path>
```

without dealing with repositories or any implementation details.

3. Possible Follow-Ups

The following steps are suggested to project partners and collaborators:

1. Finalize and publish v1.0 release of [nf-core/genomicrelatedness](#) upon approval of the nf-core community.
2. Add additional relatedness estimation modules once licensing and packaging constraints of external software are resolved.

Bibliography

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